

ASSESSING THE GENDER SENSITIVITY AND GENDER EQUALITY AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Assessing the Gender Sensitivity and Gender Equality Among Senior High School Students

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Abstract. The study aimed to examine the level of gender sensitivity perceived by the students across the different dimensions of gender equality—cognitive, affective, and behavioural. It further sought to determine whether senior high school students at ZCSA perceive the educational environment's gender sensitivity and gender equality dimensions to be significantly correlated, as well as whether significant differences are present in the respondents' perceptions of gender sensitivity and gender equality when grouped according to their demographic profile. A descriptive-correlational research design was used, and data were gathered using a structured survey questionnaire, which serves as a primary data-gathering tool. A total of 183 out of 346 SHS students were selected using Cochran's formula and stratified random sampling was employed to ensure that respondents are equally distributed according to their strand: the STEM, HUMSS, and TVL strands. The results show a significant positive correlation between the perceived gender-sensitive initiatives and the advancement of gender equality. Gender equality improves when students' perceptions of teachers' approaches and the school environment are positive and promote gender awareness and inclusivity. Significant differences in the perceptions of gender sensitivity and gender equality were found when respondents were grouped according to their sex and grade level. However, significant differences were found in the perceptions of gender sensitivity when grouped according to their strand, while no significant difference in the perceptions of gender equality. In conclusion, the educational environment at ZCSAI is highly conducive to fostering gender awareness, which is supported by the high levels of perceived gender sensitivity and the strong positive features of gender equality that the students reported.

Keywords: Curricular Content, Gender Equality, Gender Sensitivity, Pedagogical Viewpoint, School Environment

Introduction

Gender sensitivity has become a crucial area of research in understanding societal dynamics, especially in education. The process through which people discover how gender affects how they behave with others is known as "gender sensitivity." It is the capability to identify, comprehend, and be conscious of gender-related issues, discrimination, and inequality in our society or in any sector. (Ruby Park Public School, 2021; Sruthi, 2024). Gender equality is the state in which access to rights or opportunities is given to all people, regardless of gender. Gender inequality affects persons of all genders, including men, transgender individuals, and those who identify as gender nonconforming. Men, women, transgender people, and gender nonconforming people shall all have equal rights, duties, and opportunities regardless of the gender they were assigned at birth (United Way NCA, 2024).

At the global level, gender sensitivity is frequently linked to development agendas on a global scale, especially in fields like economic participation, health, and education. Gender-sensitive approaches must be thoroughly understood and integrated in order to advance gender equality globally. Despite making up 70% of the worldwide health and social care workforce, only 25% of top leadership roles are held by women (The United Nations Development Program 2020). Nationally, with laws like the Magna Carta of Women

(Republic Act No. 9710), the Philippines has significantly advanced gender equality at the national level. Teachers use techniques including gender-neutral language and group activities to promote equality despite facing obstacles connected to gender stereotypes, bias, and discrimination (Quezon City University 2024). In local studies conducted Zamboanga City show how difficult it is for communities to deal with gender-based violence and prejudice. Through collaborations between the local administration and the Local Council of Women, Zamboanga City is strengthening its commitment to gender equality. These partnerships support programs that address gender-based violence, discrimination, and women's empowerment (Philippine Information Agency 2025; Espinosa 2025).

The gaps in gender sensitivity research at the international, national, and local levels are apparent in the absence of frameworks that are inclusive and culturally appropriate. Western viewpoints are disproportionately central to global studies. In the Philippines, national studies frequently ignore regional variations, while at the local level, places like Geographical differences and sociocultural diversity present special problems for Zamboanga City.

The primary objective of this study was to determine whether a significant relationship existed between the perceived gender sensitivity of the educational environment and the dimensions of gender equality among senior high school students at ZCSAI. The study also sought to determine whether there were significant differences in perceptions when respondents were grouped according to their demographic profiles. Although gender equality research has been extensive, it often overlooks private schools and focuses on general perceptions or single-gender views. Existing research had largely been conducted in public schools and universities, leaving private school environments insufficiently examined. This study aims to fill these gaps by providing insights that could enhance gender sensitivity programmes within these distinct educational environments.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine how senior high school students in ZCSAI perceived gender sensitivity in the educational environment in relation to the multifaceted dimensions of gender equality. It also sought to examine whether students' perceptions differed when they were grouped according to their demographic profiles.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the senior high school students in terms of
 - 1.1 Sex;
 - 1.2 Strand; and
 - 1.3 Grade Level
2. What is the level of gender sensitivity in ZCSAI as perceived by the students across the following areas:
 - 2.1 Pedagogical Viewpoint
 - 2.2 Curricular Content
 - 2.3 School Environment
3. What is the level of the multifaceted dimensions of gender equality among the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1 Cognitive
 - 3.2 Affective
 - 3.3 Behavioral
4. Is there any significant relationship between perceived gender sensitivity in education and the dimensions of gender equality among the respondents?
5. Is there a significant difference in the perceptions of gender sensitivity and gender equality when respondents are grouped according to their profile?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study examined whether a significant relationship existed between the perceived gender sensitivity of the educational environment and the dimensions of gender equality—cognitive, affective, and behavioral—among senior high school students at Z.C. Skills Academy, Inc. (ZCSAI), Baliwasan Chico, Zamboanga City, during the school year 2024–2026. It also determined whether differences in perceptions of gender sensitivity and gender equality existed when respondents were grouped according to sex, strand (STEM, HUMSS, and TVL), and grade level (Grade 11 and Grade 12). The study involved 183 respondents selected from a population of 347 students using Cochran's formula and stratified random sampling. A descriptive-correlational research design with structured survey questionnaires was used. The study was limited to one institution and relied solely on quantitative data, excluding qualitative methods and other factors such as exposure to queer literature, intersectional variables, and familial or societal influences, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.

Literature Review

Many studies and literatures highlight the importance of education in promoting gender equality and understanding among students. According to both domestic and foreign sources, schools play a crucial role in shaping gender-related beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours. According to studies by Habib et al. (2020), Fithriani (2022), and Aguilar-Delavin (2022), gender stereotypes and unequal representation in textbooks and other materials are still prevalent and can influence students' perceptions of gender roles. Losioki and Mdee (2023) similarly explained how the hidden curriculum found in educational materials may inadvertently support the reinforcement of gender bias. In the meantime, organisations like UNESCO, UNICEF, and the OECD emphasised that fostering inclusive schools, employing inclusive teaching strategies, and being conscious of gender issues are crucial steps in advancing equality and reducing discrimination in education. Kalra et al. (2021) emphasized that programs aimed at gender sensitivity in schools reduce stereotypes and create equitable opportunities for learners. Additionally, Li, (2022) discussed how educational systems can foster gender equality by developing and promoting inclusive practices and empowering all students regardless of sex.

Similarly, other research has demonstrated that gender-conscious teaching strategies, educational initiatives, and course designs can improve students' comprehension of equality in terms of thinking, feeling, and behaving. According to research by Ballado et al. (2022), Canuto and Espique (2022), and Casas et al. (2024), employing strategies like inclusive teaching, gender-neutral language, and teamwork in the classroom can improve students' attitudes and awareness of gender equality. Furthermore, research by Orfan and Samady (2023) and Sherazi and Khalid (2024) showed that although students generally have favourable opinions on gender equality, their opinions can vary depending on things like gender, academic focus, or cultural background. According to Tejada (2025) and Agupitan (2025), administrative support, gender-sensitive school policies, and peer support systems are essential in supporting the implementation of gender equity initiatives within educational institutions. De Jesus et al, 2022 also concluded that the exposure of students to inclusive literature can increase their sensitivity and awareness towards gender. In addition, De Jesus et al. (2022) found that exposure to inclusive literary materials can enhance students' gender sensitivity and awareness.

There are evident gaps — even though the research literature are somewhat growing to support gender sensitivity (GS) and promote gender equality. A number of international studies are either limited to western countries, or other national studies in the Philippines are specific to schools and universities. Furthermore, few studies have examined gender sensitivity in private secondary schools like Zamboanga City, which presents a diverse local context. Such gaps indicate that it is worth further exploring how gender-sensitive educational environments impact the multi-faceted dimensions of gender equality among senior high school students.

Therefore, the purpose of this research is to investigate how factors such as how gender sensitivity of an educational institution affects the overall gender equity of the institution. The goal of this research is to provide insight into the ways that schools can create an environment that promotes women's issues and supports the equality of girls and boys within that environment.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to assess students' perceptions of gender sensitivity and gender equality. According to Barooah (2025), using this design helps the researchers to observe and analyze how two or more characteristics interacted in their natural settings. The descriptive aspect aimed to determine the level of gender sensitivity in Z.C. Skills Academy, Inc. and describe students' perceptions of gender equality across cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions, as well as differences based on demographic profiles such as sex, strand, and grade level. The correlational aspect sought to identify whether a significant relationship or difference existed between the perceived gender sensitivity and the dimensions of gender equality among senior high school students. This design allowed the researchers to analyze patterns and relationships among the variables relevant to the study.

Sampling Design

The study used probability sampling, specifically stratified random sampling, to ensure proper representation of subgroups within the population. Stratified random sampling involves dividing a population into smaller subgroups, or strata, based on shared characteristics of the members (Simkus, 2023). The total of 183 respondents are equally distributed across strands—61 in STEM, 61 in HUMSS, and 61 in TVL—and respondents were randomly selected from each group. This method was appropriate because the senior high school population was already divided into distinct strands, allowing the study to obtain more accurate and representative responses.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Z.C. Skills Academy, Inc. (ZCSAI) is located at Baliwasan Chico, Zamboanga City, Philippines. This institution was a private school located 2.1 kilometers northeast of the city proper of Zamboanga. It had a campus area of 300 square meters and was housed in a four-story building. The school had a total population of 522 senior high school students who were currently enrolled during the academic year 2025–2026, with 13 senior high school teachers.

Research Participants

This study included only regular senior high school students in ZCSAI, with a total of 347 students across three strands: 117 in STEM, 129 in HUMMS, and 101 in TVL (HE/ICT) grades 11 and 12 who are currently enrolled in S.Y. 2025-2026. 183 out of 347 students were selected using Cochran's formula. Respondents are equally distributed across strands, with a total of 61 students in each strand. These selected students served as the respondents and the primary source of data on gender sensitivity and gender equality in education at ZCSAI.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a research-made structured survey questionnaire to assess gender sensitivity and gender equality perceptions among senior high school students at Z.C. Skills Academy, Inc. (ZCSAI). The questionnaire had three parts: Part I gathered the respondents' demographic information (sex, strand, and grade level); Part II assessed students' perceptions of gender sensitivity in terms of pedagogical practices, curricular content, and the school environment; and Part III examined the cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions of gender equality. A 5-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5) was used to measure responses, and the collected data were analyzed quantitatively using appropriate statistical tools to determine relationships and differences among the variables.

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure the proper way of gathering data, the following procedures are adhered to. First, the researchers seek formal permission from the school head to conduct a study, submitting a detailed request letter outlining the research's purpose and methodology. Once approval was granted, the researchers distributed the questionnaires personally to the selected ZCSAI students; after answers were given, the questionnaires were retrieved. Administered without disrupting classes, students received 20 minutes to complete the questionnaires, which are then sealed for privacy. After retrieval, responses are organized in Excel and analyzed with statistical tools, guided by a statistician. The findings, focusing on gender sensitivity in education, are interpreted and verified before preparing a comprehensive report for the school administration and research adviser.

Results and Discussions

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the senior high school students in terms of sex, strand, and grade level.

Table 1. Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of sex.

Sex	Frequency	Percentages
Male	85	46.45
Female	98	53.55
Total	183	100

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex. The highest frequency is 98 respondents, or 53.55%, who are female senior high school students. The remaining respondents are male senior high school students, with a frequency of 85 respondents, or 46.45%. The results show that most of the respondents fall under the female category, with a frequency of 98 or 53.55%.

Table 2. Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of strand.

Strand	Frequency	Percentage
STEM	61	33.33
HUMSS	61	33.33
TVL	61	33.33
Total	183	100

Table 2 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of strand. The respondents are evenly distributed according to strand—the STEM, HUMMS, and TVL strands have the same frequency and percentage. The equal distribution of participants across the three strands shows that the research findings provide a fair representation of students from each strand at ZCSAI.

Table 3. Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of grade level.

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 11	81	44.26
Grade 12	102	55.74
Total	183	100

Table 3 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of grade level. The highest frequency is 102 respondents, or 55.74%, who are grade 12 senior high school students. The remaining respondents are grade 11 senior high school students, with a frequency of 81 respondents, or 44.26%. The results show that most of the respondents fall under the grade 12 category, with a frequency of 102 or 55.74%.

Problem 2: What is the level of gender sensitivity in ZCSAI as perceived by the students across the following areas: pedagogical viewpoint, curricular content, school environment.

Table 4: The Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the Perceived Gender Sensitivity in Education in terms of Pedagogical Viewpoint.

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Teachers use gender-inclusive language (everyone or students).	3.90	Agree
2. Teachers call on students to answer questions regardless of their sex/gender.	3.69	Agree
3. Classroom leadership roles are assigned based on merit, not gender.	3.89	Agree
4. Teachers provide equal praise to both male and female students.	3.78	Agree
5. Teachers discourage gender-based bullying or teasing immediately.	4.01	Agree
6. Group activities are formed to encourage mixing of different genders.	3.91	Agree
7. Teachers avoid using gender stereotypes to explain concepts.	3.97	Agree
8. Disciplining of students is consistent regardless of their sex.	3.90	Agree
9. Teachers encourage all students to pursue any career path they desire.	4.00	Agree
10. Teachers are approachable regarding gender-related concerns.	3.98	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.90	Agree

Table 4 displays the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the perceived gender sensitivity in education in terms of pedagogical viewpoint. The highest mean of 4.01 was observed in Statement 5, which states, "Teachers discourage gender-based bullying or teasing immediately", with a verbal interpretation of "Agree". On the other hand, Statement 2, which reads, "Teachers call on students to answer questions regardless of their sex/gender", had the lowest mean of 3.69 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree". The overall mean of 3.90 is interpreted as "Agree", indicating that pedagogical viewpoints are generally perceived as gender-sensitive in the classroom. The findings suggested that senior high school students in ZCSAI perceived its institutions' pedagogical viewpoint as gender-sensitive. However, the lowest mean of 3.69 implying that some teachers' teaching methods doesn't help in promoting gender equality. These findings align with Canuto and Espique (2022), who emphasized that gender-responsive pedagogical practices—such as providing equal participation opportunities, using mixed-gender group activities, and promptly addressing gender-based discrimination—play a key role in fostering gender equality in secondary schools.

Table 5: The Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the Perceived Gender Sensitivity in Education in terms of Curricular Content

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Textbooks present men and women in equal and diverse roles without gender bias.	4.04	Agree
2. Our lessons highlight the achievements of women in science and history.	4.01	Agree
3. Instructional materials avoid portraying women as only "homemakers."	3.90	Agree
4. Examples used in math or science problems involve all genders equally.	4.00	Agree
5. The curriculum includes topics on gender rights and sensitivity.	3.98	Agree
6. Visual aids in the classroom show diverse gender representations.	3.86	Agree
7. School modules challenge the idea that certain subjects are "for boys" or "for girls."	3.87	Agree
8. Literature discussed in class includes diverse gender perspectives.	3.70	Agree
9. The school provides seminars or workshops on gender equality.	3.81	Agree
10. Educational videos shown in class are free from gender bias.	3.84	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.90	Agree

Table 5 presents the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the perceived gender sensitivity in education in terms of curricular content. The highest mean of 4.04 was observed in Statement 1, which states, "Textbooks show men and women performing the same types of jobs," with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." The lowest mean of 3.70 was recorded in Statement 8, which states, "Literature discussed in class includes diverse gender perspectives," with the verbal interpretation of "Agree." The overall mean of 3.90 is interpreted as "Agree", indicating that the curricular content is generally perceived as gender-sensitive, with some areas requiring further enhancement. These findings suggest that senior high school students perceive the curricular content at ZCSAI generally as a gender-sensitive institution. The lowest mean of 3.70 indicates that learning materials doesn't really include equal gender perspectives. The results are aligned with studies like Losioki and Mdee (2023), who noted that while textbooks increasingly represent both genders, subtle

biases may persist if learning materials are not carefully designed. Similarly, Kencana and Susanti (2025) reported that inclusive content and balanced representation reduce gender stereotypes and promote fairness. In the Philippine context, Aguilar-Delavin (2022) found that gender-balanced English modules influence students' perceptions of gender roles.

Table 6: The Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the Perceived Gender Sensitivity in Education in terms of School Environment

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. The school provides adequate and private comfort rooms for all.	3.88	Agree
2. School policies are written in a way that respects all gender identities.	3.72	Agree
3. Sports facilities and equipment are accessible to everyone.	3.70	Agree
4. There are clear posters or signs promoting gender respect in the halls.	3.81	Agree
5. Enrollment and scholarship processes are fair to all genders.	3.84	Agree
6. The school clinic provides equal care to all students.	3.82	Agree
7. Security personnel treat all students with equal respect.	3.83	Agree
8. School clubs and organizations are open to all, regardless of sex.	3.96	Agree
9. The student handbook has clear rules against sexual harassment.	3.81	Agree
10. The school campus feels like a safe space for every student.	3.90	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.83	Agree

Table 6 shows the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the perceived gender sensitivity in education in terms of school environment. The highest mean of 3.96 was observed in Statement 8, which states, "School clubs and organisations are open to all, regardless of sex," with a verbal interpretation of "Agree". Statement 3, which states, "Sports facilities and equipment are accessible to everyone," had the lowest mean of 3.70 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree". The overall mean of 3.83 is interpreted as "Agree", indicating that senior high school students generally perceive their school environment as gender-sensitive and supportive of gender equality. The findings indicate that senior high school students at ZCSAI perceived the institutions' environment as gender-sensitive and supportive. Moreover, the lowest mean of 3.70 highlights that not all the time that the facilities are accessible to all. These findings are supported by the study of Tamang et al. (2025), who demonstrated that both physical facilities and the social climate influence students' sense of inclusion and fairness.

Problem 3: What is the level of the multifaceted dimensions of gender equality among the respondents in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral.

Table 7: The Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the Perceived Gender Sensitivity in Education in terms of Cognitive Dimension

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I believe that intelligence is not determined by a person's sex.	3.95	Agree
2. I believe that both men and women can be effective emotional leaders.	3.91	Agree
3. I believe that household chores should be shared equally by all.	3.96	Agree
4. I believe that men and women should receive the same pay for the same work.	3.93	Agree
5. I believe that gender equality benefits the whole society.	3.96	Agree
6. I believe that everyone should have the right to express their identity.	3.81	Agree
7. I believe that strength is not a trait exclusive to men.	3.90	Agree
8. I believe that empathy is not a trait exclusive to women.	3.97	Agree
9. I believe that all strands (STEM, HUMSS, TVL) are suitable for any gender.	3.95	Agree
10. I believe that education is the key to achieving gender fairness.	3.87	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.92	Agree

Table 7 demonstrates the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on gender sensitivity and gender equality in education in terms of the cognitive dimension. The highest mean of 3.97 was observed in Statement 8, which states, "I believe that empathy is not a trait exclusive to women," with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." In contrast, the lowest mean of 3.81 falls under Statement 6, which states, "I believe that everyone should have the right to express their identity," also interpreted as "Agree." The overall mean of 3.92 is interpreted as "Agree," indicating that students generally hold positive and gender-equitable beliefs, reflecting a strong cognitive awareness and understanding of gender equality principles in education. The findings show that ZCSAI students hold positive and gender-equality beliefs, demonstrating strong cognitive awareness of gender equality in education while suggesting that having the right to express could enhance understanding. Similarly, the study by Pérez Díaz et al. (2025) found that students' social attitudes and understanding of equality shape how they perceive gender roles. Likewise, Mosquida and Muegna (2025) indicated that there's a high overall awareness of gender equality among education students.

Table 8: The Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the Perceived Gender Sensitivity in Education in terms of Affective Dimension

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I feel comfortable when a different gender leads my group.	3.91	Agree
2. I feel respected by my peers of the opposite sex.	3.94	Agree
3. I am willing to support school campaigns for gender equality.	3.97	Agree
4. I feel that it is okay for anyone to cry or show vulnerability.	3.95	Agree
5. I am not offended when someone challenges my views on gender.	3.87	Agree
6. I feel proud when my school promotes gender-inclusive events.	3.92	Agree
7. I am empathetic toward those who experience gender discrimination.	3.91	Agree
8. I feel confident that I can succeed regardless of my gender.	3.92	Agree
9. I value the opinions of my classmates equally, regardless of sex.	3.98	Agree
10. I feel safe expressing my true self within the ZCSAI community.	3.97	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.93	Agree

Table 8 presents the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on gender sensitivity and gender equality in education in terms of the affective dimension. The highest mean was observed in statement 9, which states, "I value the opinions of my classmates equally, regardless of sex," having a mean of 3.98, with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.87 was recorded in statement 5, which states, "I am not offended when someone challenges my views on gender," with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." The overall mean is 3.92, interpreted as "Agree," indicating that students generally exhibit positive attitudes and emotional support toward gender equality. The findings indicate that students in ZCSAI exhibit positive attitudes toward gender equality, feeling respected, confident, and included within its environment, while showcasing opportunities to further strengthen flexibility when facing challenges. The findings are supported by Casas et al. (2024) who reported that students exposed to gender sensitivity programs demonstrated high awareness and positive attitudes toward gender rights, showing empathy and confidence in interactions with diverse peers.

Table 9: The Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on the Perceived Gender Sensitivity in Education in terms of Behavioral Dimension

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I use gender-neutral terms when talking to my classmates.	3.96	Agree
2. I actively partner with different genders during laboratory work.	3.99	Agree
3. I speak up when I hear someone making a sexist joke.	4.01	Agree
4. I share school responsibilities equally with my group mates.	3.90	Agree
5. I avoid judging others based on their choice of clothes or grooming.	3.92	Agree
6. I include everyone in playtime or social activities.	3.98	Agree
7. I vote for student leaders based on platforms, not their gender.	3.97	Agree
8. I help my peers understand the importance of respecting all genders.	3.97	Agree
9. I treat every person I meet with the same level of dignity.	3.96	Agree
10. I participate in school discussions regarding gender sensitivity.	3.99	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.97	Agree

Table 9 introduces the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) for Gender Sensitivity and Gender Equality in Education, focusing on the Behavioral Dimension. The highest mean of 4.01 is for the statement "I speak up when I hear someone making a sexist joke," indicating agreement, while the lowest mean of 3.90 pertains to the statement "I share school responsibilities equally with my group mates," also interpreted as agreement. The overall mean of 3.97 interpreted as "Agree" which suggests that students display generally positive gender-sensitive behaviors, promoting equality and respect in their interactions. This result indicates that students in ZCSAI exhibit positive behaviors that promote equality and inclusivity, though further encouragement of equal participation in shared responsibilities is suggested. Research by Orfan and Samady (2023) supports these results, as it shows students recognize the importance of gender equality and engage in positive actions, reflecting respect and inclusion in their daily school interactions.

Table 10: The Summary of The Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) on Gender Sensitivity and Gender Equality in Education in Terms of the Level of Perceived Gender Sensitivity and Different Dimensions of Gender Equality.

Variables	WAM	Verbal Description
Pedagogical Viewpoint	3.90	Agree
Curricular Content	3.90	Agree
School Environment	3.83	Agree
Cognitive	3.92	Agree
Affective	3.93	Agree
Behavioral	3.97	Agree

Table 10 displays the overall WAM for each indicator. The variable "Behavioral" has the highest mean, which is 3.97 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." The lowest mean is 3.83, which falls under the variable "School Environment," with a verbal interpretation of "Agree." This indicates students generally perceive their education as gender-sensitive, with the strongest demonstration in behaviors promoting

equality, while aspects of the school environment show slightly lower, yet still positive, gender sensitivity. This findings shows that students generally agree that their education is gender-sensitive across all measured dimensions—pedagogical viewpoint, curricular content, school environment, cognitive, affective, and behavioral. This indicates that respondents view their school as promoting equality, respect, and inclusivity in various aspects of learning and interaction. According to Sherazi and Khalid (2024), students’ positive perception of gender equality in education encourages fair treatment, equal participation, and active engagement in classroom activities.

Problem 4: Is there any significant relationship between perceived gender sensitivity in education and the dimensions of gender equality among the respondents.

Table 11: Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Between Perceived Gender Sensitivity and Dimensions of Gender Equality

Variable being Correlated	df	t-value	Spearman Rho (r)	p-value	Decision	Impression at 0.05 level of significance
Pedagogical Viewpoint and Dimensions of Gender Equality	181	15.038	0.745	0.001	Reject the Null Hypothesis	Significant
Curricular Content and Dimensions of Gender Equality	181	17.213	0.788	0.001	Reject the Null Hypothesis	Significant
School Environment and Dimensions of Gender Equality	181	17.309	0.790	0.001	Reject the Null Hypothesis	Significant

Table 11 presents the correlation between perceived gender sensitivity—specifically through Pedagogical Viewpoint, Curricular Content, and School Environment—and the various Dimensions of Gender Equality. Across all three variables, the Spearman rho (rs) values are quite high, ranging from 0.745 to 0.790. The p-values for all correlations are 0.001, which is below the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected in every case, marking the relationships as statistically significant. These results indicate a strong positive relationship between the school’s gender-sensitive efforts and the promotion of gender equality. The highest correlation ($r = 0.790$) belongs to the school environment, suggesting that the physical and social atmosphere of the school plays a vital role in how equality is perceived and practiced. According to Skol Forkinings Instutet (2024), proactive and intentional efforts to advance gender equality in the classroom can support equal opportunity for boys and girls as well as environments that support their growth and learning. Similarly, Droussi et al. (2025) identified areas for improvement, such as developing gender-sensitive tactics and successfully resolving gender disparities, while also highlighting the strengths in teachers' dedication to equal chances.

Problem 5: Is there a significant difference in the perceptions of gender sensitivity and gender equality when grouped according to their profile.

Table 12: Significant difference of the Perceptions on Gender Sensitivity and Gender Equality in terms of Sex using Mann-Whitney U

Dependent Variable	Sex	N	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision	Impression at 0.05 level of significance
Gender Sensitivity	Male	85	96.02	0.341	Failed to reject the null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Female	98	88.52			
Gender Equality	Male	85	95.14	0.458	Failed to reject the null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Female	98	89.28			
	Total	183				

Table 12 shows the results of the Mann-Whitney U test, which was used to determine if there is a significant difference in how males and females perceive gender sensitivity and gender equality. For gender sensitivity, the mean rank for males is 96.02, while females have a mean rank of 88.52. The calculated U value is 4505.500 with an asymptotic significance (p-value) of .341. Regarding gender equality, males show a mean rank of 95.14 compared to 89.28 for females. This variable yielded a U-value of 4430.500 and a p-value of .458. The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of gender sensitivity and gender equality between the two sexes, as both p-values are greater than the 0.05 alpha level. This suggests that regardless of whether a respondent is male or female, their understanding and views on these gender-related issues remain relatively similar. Similarly, Gustilo et al. (2025) discovered that when respondents

were categorized by age and sex, there were no discernible differences in their attitudes and perceptions of GIL; however, when the same respondents were categorized by the programs they were enrolled in, there were.

Table 13: Significant difference of the Perceptions on Gender Sensitivity and Gender Equality in terms of Strand using Kruskal Wallis H-Test

Variable	Strand	N	Mean Rank	P-value	Decision	Impression at 0.05 level of significance
Gender Sensitivity	Strand 1	61	108.52	0.014	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant
	Strand 2	61	86.84			
	Strand 3	61	80.64			
Gender Equality	Strand 1	61	101.44	0.105	Failed to reject the null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Strand 2	61	83.18			

Table 13 presents the comparison of perceptions across three strands using the Kruskal-Wallis HTest. For Gender Sensitivity, the resulting p-value of 0.014 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the decision to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that there is a significant difference in how students from different strands perceive gender sensitivity, with Strand 1 showing the highest mean rank of 108.52. Conversely, for gender equality, the p-value of 0.105 is greater than 0.05, resulting in a failure to reject the null hypothesis. This means there is no significant difference in the perceptions of gender equality among the three groups, as their mean ranks (101.44, 83.18, and 91.38) are statistically similar. These results indicate that while students across all strands have a relatively unified understanding or attitude toward gender equality, their awareness or experiences regarding gender sensitivity vary depending on their specific academic track. The presence of significant differences in the perceptions of gender sensitivity is similar to the study Monleon and Balsomo (2023) who found that while the academic strand/track of learners resulted in a significant difference to their gender expression. The absence of significant differences in gender equality perceptions is supported by Tenedero et al. (2025), whose ANOVA results revealed no statistically significant differences among student groups, indicating a generally uniform perception of gender equality.

Table 14: Significant difference of the Perceptions on Gender Sensitivity and Gender Equality in terms of Grade Level using Mann-Whitney U

Dependent Variable	Grade Level	N	Mean Rank	p-value	Decision	Impression at 0.05 level of significance
Gender Sensitivity	Grade 11	81	99.07	.065	Failed to reject the null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Grade 12	102	86.39			
Gender Equality	Grade 11	81	98.56	.084	Failed to reject the null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Grade 12	102	86.80			

The table 14 introduces the comparison of perceptions regarding Gender Sensitivity and Gender Equality between Grade 11 and Grade 12 students using the Mann-Whitney U test. For Gender Sensitivity, Grade 11 students had a mean rank of 99.07, while Grade 12 students had a mean rank of 86.39, resulting in a p-value of .065. For Gender Equality, Grade 11 students recorded a mean rank of 98.56 compared to 86.80 for Grade 12, with a p-value of .084. The findings indicate that there is no significant difference in how Grade 11 and Grade 12 students perceive gender sensitivity and gender equality. This suggests that the maturity level or the one-year gap between these two senior high school levels does not drastically change their outlook on gender issues. The findings of Agupitan (2025) demonstrated that peer acceptance, inclusive education policy, and gender-responsive teaching and learning all have a favourable impact on gender sensitivity, with respondents largely agreeing on their efficacy.

Ethical Considerations

The study followed several ethical considerations to protect the respondents. To protect the responders, the study adhered to a number of ethical guidelines. Before taking part in the study, participants willingly signed a consent form after being fully informed about its goals, methods, rights, and any dangers. Respondents were handled with respect without any force or improper influence, and participation was entirely voluntary. The researchers made sure that no vulnerable people were involved and that the subjects' wellbeing and dignity were respected. The Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act 10173) was followed in maintaining privacy and secrecy, and codes were used to protect respondents' identity. After five years of safe storage, all gathered material was disposed of appropriately by shredding

physical documents and securely erasing electronic files. Transparency and honesty were additionally stressed, urging participants to provide honest responses and voice any issues throughout the study procedure.

Conclusion

The study concludes that ZCSAI's educational environment fosters gender awareness, indicated by high gender sensitivity and positive gender equality perceptions among students. It highlights the connection between gender-sensitive teaching, inclusive content, and supportive settings, which shape students' beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors towards equality. The findings reveal consistent perceptions among students, regardless of sex or grade, but variations across academic strands indicate the influence of a student's field of study on their exposure to gender concepts. The research confirms a significant link between the educational environment and gender equality dimensions, emphasizing the school's role in shaping perspectives. ZCSAI has laid a foundation for gender-responsive education, but continuous improvements in classroom materials and equal access to facilities are needed to address remaining gaps.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it recommends that students be encouraged to actively promote equality by speaking out against sexism and participating in inclusive school organizations. Meanwhile, educators should employ gender-responsive teaching methods, use gender-neutral language, and address gender-based bullying promptly. It also recommends that school administrators need to enhance policies supporting a gender-sensitive curriculum and equitable resource distribution, particularly in sports facilities. Additionally, curriculum developers must ensure learning materials reflect diverse gender identities and roles. Future research should examine the intersectionality of gender with other identities, utilizing qualitative methods to gain deeper insights into educational experiences.

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